

On Solving Third, Fourth and Fifth Order of Reverse Fibonacci-Like Sequences

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Abstract:

This paper introduced the reverse Fibonacci-like sequences of third (reverse Tribonacci sequence), fourth (reverse Tetranacci sequence) and fifth (reverse Pentanacci sequence) orders as well as its generalization, that is, when the initial terms are not fixed. Formulas for the initial terms of the reverse Tribonacci-like, reverse Tetranacci-like and reverse Pentanacci-like sequences were derived and the numerical coefficients of these formulas were tabulated in order to derive an explicit formula for solving its n^{th} term K_n , L_n

and M_n , respectively. Moreover, the Principle of Mathematical Induction was used to validate the derived formulas for any value of n . Furthermore, it can be concluded that it is possible to generate n^{th} term formulas for the reverse Fibonacci-like sequence of higher order.

Keywords: *reverse Pentanacci sequence, reverse Tetranacci sequence, reverse Tribonacci sequence, reverse Fibonacci-like sequence of higher order.*

Introduction

The Fibonacci sequence is defined by the recurrence equation $F_n = F_{n-1} + F_{n-2}$ with initial terms $F_0 = 0$ and $F_1 = 1$. The Fibonacci sequence of third (Tribonacci), fourth (Tetranacci), fifth (Pentanacci) and sixth (Hexanacci) orders are known as Fibonacci-like sequences of higher order. If the initial terms of this sequences are not fixed, the word “like” will be added to its original name. Some of these sequences are Tribonacci-like, Tetranacci-like, Pentanacci-like, Hexanacci-like and among others (Natividad, 2013).

In 2013, Natividad and Policarpio derived a formula in solving n^{th} term of the Tribonacci-like sequence using its first three terms and Tribonacci numbers. The formula is given by the equation

$$S_n = T_{n-2}S_1 + (T_{n-2} + T_{n-3})S_2 + T_{n-1}S_3,$$

where $n \geq 4$. In the same year, Natividad provided the formulas for Fibonacci-like sequence of orders four (Tetranacci-like sequence), five (Pentanacci-like sequence) and six (Hexanacci-like sequence), and is given by the equations

$$Z_n = Y_{n-2}Z_1 + (Y_{n-2} + Y_{n-3})Z_2 + (Y_{n-2} + Y_{n-3} + Y_{n-4})Z_3 + Y_{n-1}Z_4,$$

$$Q_n = P_{n-2}Q_1 + (P_{n-2} + P_{n-3})Q_2 + (P_{n-2} + P_{n-3} + P_{n-4})Q_3 + (P_{n-2} + P_{n-3} + P_{n-4} + P_{n-5})Q_4 + P_{n-1}Q_5,$$

And

$$I_n = H_{n-2}I_1 + (H_{n-2} + H_{n-3})I_2 + (H_{n-2} + H_{n-3} + H_{n-4})I_3 + (H_{n-2} + H_{n-3} + H_{n-4} + H_{n-5})I_4 + (H_{n-2} + H_{n-3} + H_{n-4} + H_{n-5} + H_{n-6})I_5 + H_{n-1}I_6,$$

respectively.

On the other hand, Janicko (2018) derived a new sequence from the sum digits of the first 24 Fibonacci numbers of which he call it the “reverse Fibonacci sequence”. He added that the reverse Fibonacci sequence represents the dying of founders in the third generation of the famous rabbit problem. This sequence is defined by the recurrence relation $J_n = 8(J_{n-1} - J_{n-2})$ for $n \geq 2$ with $J_0 = 0$ and $J_1 = 1$ as initial terms. In 2019, Soucek and Janicko introduced the geometric properties and the Binet-type formula of the reverse Fibonacci sequence which is the equation

$$J_n = \frac{(4+2\sqrt{2})^n - (4-2\sqrt{2})^n}{4\sqrt{2}}.$$

Moreover, Elizalde and Patan (2022) derived and proved a formula for solving the first missing term or mean (x_1) of the reverse Fibonacci sequence and is given by the formula

$$x_1 = \frac{b+J_n 8a}{J_{n+1}}.$$

However, there are no equations have been formulated for the reverse Fibonacci-like sequence of higher orders. Thus, this study aimed to introduce the recurrence equation for the third, fourth, and fifth order of the reverse Fibonacci-like sequences and provide its generalized n^{th} formula as well.

Results and Discussion

This section will present the proposed definitions and formulas for the reverse

Fibonacci-like sequence of third, fourth and fifth orders.

Definition 1. The reverse Tribonacci sequence is a sequence defined by the recurrence relation $R_n = 8(R_{n-1} - R_{n-2} - R_{n-3})$ for $n \geq 3$, with $R_0 = R_1 = 0$ and $R_2 = 1$. Moreover, the sequence $K_1, K_2, K_3, \dots, K_n$, in which $K_n = 8(K_{n-1} - K_{n-2} - K_{n-3})$, is a generalized reverse Tribonacci sequence (reverse Tribonacci-like sequence).

From the recurrence formula for reverse Tribonacci sequence in the above definition, the first 10 reverse Tribonacci numbers is given by the sequence

0, 1, 8, 56, 376, 2496, 16512, 109120, 720896, 4762112, ...

To find the general formula for the n^{th} term of the reverse Tribonacci sequence, the following equations were derived, and a formula was deduced. From Definition 1, the following equations were obtained:

$$K_4 = 8(K_3 - K_2 - K_1)$$

$$K_5 = 8(7K_3 - 9K_2 - 8K_1)$$

$$K_6 = 8(47K_3 - 64K_2 - 56K_1)$$

$$K_7 = 8(312K_3 - 432K_2 - 376K_1)$$

Table 1. Coefficients of K_1, K_2 and K_3 of n^{th} term of reverse Tribonacci-like sequence

Number of terms	n^{th} term of the sequence	K_3	K_2	K_1
4	K_4	1	1	1
5	K_5	7	9	8
6	K_6	47	64	56
7	K_7	312	432	376
.
.
.
n	K_n	$R_{n-2} - R_{n-3} - R_{n-4}$	$R_{n-2} + R_{n-3}$	R_{n-2}

Theorem 1. For any real numbers K_1, K_2 and K_3 , the formula for finding n^{th} term of reverse Tribonacci-like sequence is

$$K_n = 8[(R_{n-2} - R_{n-3} - R_{n-4}) K_3 - (R_{n-2} + R_{n-3}) K_2 - R_{n-2} K_1], \quad (1)$$

where R_{n-2}, R_{n-3} , and R_{n-4} are the corresponding reverse Tribonacci numbers.

Proof(By induction for $n \geq 4$). Let $P(n)$ be

$$K_n = 8[(R_{n-2} - R_{n-3} - R_{n-4}) K_3 - (R_{n-2} + R_{n-3}) K_2 - R_{n-2} K_1], \quad \text{where } n \geq 4.$$

For $n = 4$,

$$\begin{aligned} K_4 &= 8[(R_{4-2} - R_{4-3} - R_{4-4}) K_3 - (R_{4-2} + R_{4-3}) K_2 - R_{4-2} K_1] \\ &= 8[(R_2 - R_1 - R_0) K_3 - (R_2 + R_1) K_2 - R_2 K_1] \\ &= 8[(1 - 0 - 0) K_3 - (1 + 0) K_2 - 1 K_1] \\ &= 8(K_3 - K_2 - K_1) \end{aligned}$$

which is true from Definition 1. Thus, $P(4)$ is true. Now, suppose that $P(k)$ is true for some integer $k = n \geq 4$, that is

$$K_k = 8[(R_{k-2} - R_{k-3} - R_{k-4}) K_3 - (R_{k-2} + R_{k-3}) K_2 - R_{k-2} K_1].$$

We need to show that $P(k+1)$ is true whenever $P(k)$ is true, that is,

$$K_{k+1} = 8[(R_{k-1} - R_{k-2} - R_{k-3}) K_3 - (R_{k-2} + R_{k-3}) K_2 - R_{k-2} K_1].$$

To verify the above equation, we shall subtract K_{k-1} and K_{k-2} to both sides of $P(k)$ and, then

multiply 8. Now, the left side of $P(k)$ will become

$$8(K_k - K_{k-1} - K_{k-2})$$

which is equal to the left side of $P(k+1)$ because $8(K_k - K_{k-1} - K_{k-2}) = K_{k+1}$, from Definition 1.

On the other hand, the right side of $P(k)$ becomes

$$8[8((R_{k-2} - R_{k-3} - R_{k-4}) K_3 - (R_{k-2} + R_{k-3}) K_2 - R_{k-2} K_1) - K_{k-1} - K_{k-2}].$$

Since

$$K_{k-1} = 8((R_{k-3} - R_{k-4} - R_{k-5}) K_3 - (R_{k-3} + R_{k-4}) K_2 - R_{k-3} K_1)$$

And

$$K_{k-2} = 8((R_{k-4} - R_{k-5} - R_{k-6}) K_3 - (R_{k-4} + R_{k-5}) K_2 - R_{k-4} K_1),$$

it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} &8[8((R_{k-2} - R_{k-3} - R_{k-4}) K_3 - (R_{k-2} + R_{k-3}) K_2 - R_{k-2} K_1) \\ &\quad - 8((R_{k-3} - R_{k-4} - R_{k-5}) K_3 - (R_{k-3} + R_{k-4}) K_2 - R_{k-3} K_1) \\ &\quad - 8((R_{k-4} - R_{k-5} - R_{k-6}) K_3 - (R_{k-4} + R_{k-5}) K_2 - R_{k-4} K_1)] \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\Rightarrow 8[(8(R_{k-2} - R_{k-3} - R_{k-4}) - 8(R_{k-3} - R_{k-4} - R_{k-5}) - 8(R_{k-4} - R_{k-5} - R_{k-6})) K_3 \\ &\quad - (8(R_{k-2} + R_{k-3}) - 8(R_{k-3} + R_{k-4}) + 8(R_{k-4} + R_{k-5})) K_2 - 8(R_{k-2} - R_{k-3} - R_{k-4}) K_1]. \end{aligned}$$

By Definition 1, the equation will become

$$8[(R_{k-1} - R_{k-2} - R_{k-3})K_3 - (R_{k-2} + R_{k-3})K_2 - R_{k-2}K_1]$$

which is the right side of $P(k+1)$. Thus, by induction on n , equation (1) is verified. ■

Definition 2. The reverse Tetranacci sequence $\{S_n\}$ is a sequence defined by the recurrence relation $S_n = 8(S_{n-1} - S_{n-2} - S_{n-3} - S_{n-4})$ for $n \geq 4$, with $S_0 = S_1 = S_2 = 0$ and $S_3 = 1$. Moreover, the sequence $L_1, L_2, L_3, L_4, \dots, L_n$ in which $L_n = 8(L_{n-1} - L_{n-2} - L_{n-3} - L_{n-4})$ is a generalized reverse Tetranacci sequence (reverse Tetranacci-Like sequence).

From Definition 2, the first 10 reverse Tetranacci numbers are

0, 0, 1, 8, 56, 367, 2488, 16384, 107712, 707712, ...

After solving the equations for L_5, L_6, L_7 and L_8 , the coefficients for L_4, L_3, L_2 and L_1 were tabulated in the following table.

Table 2. Coefficients of L_1, L_2, L_3 and L_4 of n^{th} term of reverse Tetranacci-Like Sequence

No. of Terms	N^{th} Term of the Sequence	L_4	L_3	L_2	L_1
5	L_5	1	1	1	1
6	L_6	7	9	9	8
7	L_7	47	65	64	56
8	L_8	311	440	432	376
.
.
.
n	L_n	$S_{n-2} - S_{n-3} - S_{n-4} - S_{n-5}$	$S_{n-2} + S_{n-3} + S_{n-4}$	$S_{n-2} + S_{n-3}$	S_{n-2}

Theorem 2. For any real numbers L_1, L_2, L_3 and L_4 , the formula for finding the n^{th} term of reverse Tetranacci-like sequence is

$$L_n = 8[(S_{n-2} - S_{n-3} - S_{n-4} - S_{n-5})L_4 - (S_{n-2} + S_{n-3} + S_{n-4})L_3 - (S_{n-2} + S_{n-3})L_2 - S_{n-2}L_1] \quad (2)$$

where $S_{n-2}, S_{n-3}, S_{n-4}$ and S_{n-5} are the corresponding reverse Tetranacci numbers.

Proof (By induction for $n \geq 5$). Assume that $P(n)$ is

$$L_n = 8((S_{n-2} - S_{n-3} - S_{n-4} - S_{n-5})L_4 - (S_{n-2} + S_{n-3} + S_{n-4})L_3 - (S_{n-2} + S_{n-3})L_2 - S_{n-2}L_1, \text{ where } n \geq 5.$$

When $n = 5$,

$$\begin{aligned} L_5 &= 8[(S_{5-2} - S_{5-3} - S_{5-4} - S_{5-5})L_4 - (S_{5-2} + S_{5-3} + S_{5-4})L_3 - (S_{5-2} + S_{5-3})L_2 - S_{5-2}L_1] \\ &= 8[(S_3 - S_2 - S_1 - S_0)L_4 - (S_3 + S_2 + S_1)L_3 - (S_3 + S_2)L_2 - S_3L_1] \\ &= 8[(1 - 0 - 0 - 0)L_4 - (1 + 0 + 0)L_3 - (1 + 0)L_2 - 8L_1] \\ &= 8[(1)L_4 - (1)L_3 - (1)L_2 - (1)L_1] \\ &= 8[L_4 - L_3 - L_2 - L_1] \end{aligned}$$

which is true from Definition 2. So, $P(5)$ is true. Now, suppose that $P(k)$ is true for some integer $k = n \geq 5$, that is,

$$L_k = 8((S_{k-2} - S_{k-3} - S_{k-4} - S_{k-5})L_4 - (S_{k-2} + S_{k-3} + S_{k-4})L_3 - (S_{k-2} + S_{k-3})L_2 - S_{k-2}L_1$$

We will prove that $P(k+1)$ is also true, that is,

$$L_{k+1} = 8((S_{k-1} - S_{k-2} - S_{k-3} - S_{k-4})L_4 - (S_{k-1} + S_{k-2} + S_{k-3})L_3 - (S_{k-1} + S_{k-2})L_2 - S_{k-1}L_1).$$

To do this, we shall subtract $L_{k-1}, L_{k-2},$ and L_{k-3} to both sides of $P(k)$ and, then multiply 8. The left side of $P(k)$ will become

$$8(L_k - L_{k-1} - L_{k-2} - L_{k-3})$$

which is the left side of $P(k+1)$ because $8(L_k - L_{k-1} - L_{k-2} - L_{k-3}) = L_{k+1},$ by Definition 2.

On the other hand, the right side of $P(k)$ becomes

$$8[8((S_{k-2} - S_{k-3} - S_{k-4} - S_{k-5})L_4 - (S_{k-2} + S_{k-3} + S_{k-4})L_3 - (S_{k-2} + S_{k-3})L_2 - S_{k-2}L_1) - L_{k-1} - L_{k-2} - L_{k-3}].$$

$$\Rightarrow 8[8((S_{k-2} - S_{k-3} - S_{k-4} - S_{k-5})L_4 - (S_{k-2} + S_{k-3} + S_{k-4})L_3 - (S_{k-2} + S_{k-3})L_2 - S_{k-2}L_1)$$

$$- 8((S_{k-3} - S_{k-4} - S_{k-5} - S_{k-6})L_4 - (S_{k-3} + S_{k-4} + S_{k-5})L_3 - (S_{k-3} + S_{k-4})L_2 - S_{k-3}L_1)$$

$$- 8((S_{k-4} - S_{k-5} - S_{k-6} - S_{k-7})L_4 - (S_{k-4} + S_{k-5} + S_{k-6})L_3 - (S_{k-4} + S_{k-5})L_2 - S_{k-4}L_1)$$

$$- 8((S_{k-5} - S_{k-6} - S_{k-7} - S_{k-8})L_4 - (S_{k-5} + S_{k-6} + S_{k-7})L_3 - (S_{k-5} + S_{k-6})L_2 - S_{k-5}L_1)].$$

$$\Rightarrow 8[8((S_{k-2} - S_{k-3} - S_{k-4} - S_{k-5}) - (S_{k-3} - S_{k-4} - S_{k-5} - S_{k-6}) - (S_{k-4} - S_{k-5} - S_{k-6} - S_{k-7}) - (S_{k-5} - S_{k-6} - S_{k-7} - S_{k-8}))L_4$$

$$- 8((S_{k-2} + S_{k-3} + S_{k-4}) - (S_{k-3} + S_{k-4} + S_{k-5}) - (S_{k-4} + S_{k-5} + S_{k-6}) - (S_{k-5} + S_{k-6} + S_{k-7}))L_3$$

$$- 8((S_{k-2} + S_{k-3}) - (S_{k-3} + S_{k-4}) - (S_{k-4} + S_{k-5}) - (S_{k-5} + S_{k-6}))L_2 - 8(S_{k-2} - S_{k-3} - S_{k-4} - S_{k-5})L_1].$$

$$\Rightarrow 8[(8(S_{k-2} - S_{k-3} - S_{k-4} - S_{k-5}) - 8(S_{k-3} - S_{k-4} - S_{k-5} - S_{k-6}) - 8(S_{k-4} - S_{k-5} - S_{k-6} - S_{k-7}) - 8(S_{k-5} - S_{k-6} - S_{k-7} - S_{k-8}))L_4 - (8(S_{k-2} - S_{k-3} - S_{k-4} - S_{k-5}) + 8(S_{k-3} - S_{k-4} - S_{k-5} - S_{k-6}) + 8(S_{k-4} - S_{k-5} - S_{k-6} - S_{k-7}))L_3 - (8(S_{k-2} - S_{k-3} - S_{k-4} - S_{k-5}) + 8(S_{k-3} - S_{k-4} - S_{k-5} - S_{k-6}))L_2 - 8(S_{k-2} - S_{k-3} - S_{k-4} - S_{k-5})L_1].$$

By Definition 2, the equation will become

$$8((S_{k-1} - S_{k-2} - S_{k-3} - S_{k-4})L_4 - (S_{k-1} + S_{k-2} + S_{k-3})L_3 - (S_{k-1} + S_{k-2})L_2 - S_{k-1}L_1)$$

which is the right side of the $P(k+1)$. Hence, by induction on n , conclusion follows. ■

Definition 3. The reverse Pentanacci sequence $\{T_n\}$ is a sequence defined by the recurrence relation $T_n = 8(T_{n-1} - T_{n-2} - T_{n-3} - T_{n-4} - T_{n-5})$ for $n \geq 5$, with $T_0 = T_1 = T_2 = T_3 = 0$ and $T_4 = 1$. Moreover, the sequence $M_1, M_2, M_3, M_4, M_5, \dots, M_n$, in which $M_n = 8(M_{n-1} - M_{n-2} - M_{n-3} - M_{n-4} - M_{n-5})$ is a generalized reverse Pentanacci sequence (reverse Pentanacci-Like sequence).

The sequence

$$0, 0, 0, 1, 8, 56, 376, 2488, 16376, 107584, \dots$$

is the first 10 reverse Pentanacci numbers.

Theorem 3. For any real numbers $M_1, M_2, M_3, M_4,$ and M_5 , the formula for finding the n^{th} term of reverse Pentanacci-like sequence is

$$M_n = 8[(T_{n-2} - T_{n-3} - T_{n-4} - T_{n-5} - T_{n-6})M_5 - (T_{n-2} + T_{n-3} + T_{n-4} + T_{n-5})M_4 - (T_{n-2} + T_{n-3} + T_{n-4})M_3 - (T_{n-2} + T_{n-3})M_2 - T_{n-2}M_1] \quad (3)$$

where T_{n-2} , T_{n-3} , T_{n-4} , T_{n-5} and T_{n-6} are the corresponding reverse Pentanacci numbers.

Proof. The proof of this theorem is the same with Theorems 1 and 2, for $n \geq 6$, and is purposely left to the reader. ■

Conclusion

In this paper, the researchers introduced a recurrence sequence for the reverse Fibonacci-like sequences of third, fourth and fifth order and provided its' general n^{th} term formula. The derived formulas were verified through the Principle of Mathematical Induction for any value of n . Thus, it is possible to generate n^{th} term formulas for reverse Fibonacci-like sequence of higher order. A further investigation of this study is to derive a formula for finding the n^{th} term of reverse Fibonacci-like sequence of m^{th} order.

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